

A Longitudinal Analysis of Renewable Energy Adoption in NSE FMCG Index Firms in the Post BRSR Period in India

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The authors declare that no funding was received for this work.

Received: 15-April-2026

Accepted: 17-May-2026

Published: 20-May-2026

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This article is published in the **MSI Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (MSIJMR)** ISSN 3049-0669 (Online)

The journal is managed and published by MSI Publishers.

Volume: 3, Issue: 5 (May-2026)

ABSTRACT: The study assesses the corporate engagement in sustainability reporting by evaluating the reported progress in renewable energy adoption by focusing on the intersection of the two key dimensions of SDG 12.6.1 which focuses on the number of companies publishing sustainability reports and SDG 7.2.1 which focuses on renewable energy share in total final energy consumption with respect to the Business Responsibility and Sustainability Reporting (BRSR) provisions in Indian context. A longitudinal analysis was carried out using a balanced panel approach for a dataset consisting of 15 companies that are a part of NIFTY FMCG Index for FY23-FY25. Census sampling technique was used with companies drawn based on their consistent and reliable BRSR disclosures. ANOVA was used to test the patterns in renewable energy consumption and moderating effect of market capitalization which showed significant increase in the mean share of renewable energy from 45.8% in Y1 to 55.2% in Y3. No significant influence of market capitalization was observed on renewable energy adoption by FMCG companies which indicates on the possibility of no role of firm size on energy choices.

Keywords: *sustainability reporting, renewable energy, SDG 7, SDG 12, FMCG India*

1. Introduction

The 2030 agenda for sustainable development, adopted by all United Nations members in the year 2015 established the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) aiming at advancing development and fostering a more favourable future. The goals include eradication of poverty, protection of the planet and shared prosperity by 2030 (United Nations, 2015). Sustainable development refers to the “development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs” (World Commission on Environment and Development, 1987). SDG 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy) and SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production) are two goals out of the total 17 goals which aim at sustainable corporate operations with regard to energy transition and efficient utilization of resources.

SDG 7 aims at providing universal access to affordable, reliable, and modern energy services and SDG 7.2 target specifically tries to put efforts to increase the share of renewable energy in the global energy mix by 2030 with the indicator 7.2.1 measuring the renewable energy share in total final energy consumption (United Nations, 2018). This indicator measures the proportion of energy from renewable sources like solar, wind, hydro, biomass and geothermal.

SDG 12 focuses on responsible consumption and production and SDG 12.6 indicator encourages companies to adopt sustainable practices and integrate sustainable reporting into their reporting cycles (United Nations Conference on Trade and Development, UNCTAD, 2019). Since the private sector has a pivotal role in advancing sustainable consumption and production, the SDG 12.6 focuses on encouraging companies to adopt sustainable practices and also to integrate the sustainability information into their reporting cycles. SDG 12.6 thus seeks to mainstream sustainability considerations in to corporate decision making and market behaviour. The primary indicator for this target, indicator 12.6.1, measures the number of companies publishing sustainability report.

The companies in today's scenario have started recognizing renewable energy transition as a survival imperative instead of a voluntary ethical practice. Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI) introduced the BRSR framework in India, one of world's fastest growing economies, which requires the top 1000 listed companies by market capitalization to furnish data from 2022-23 about their environmental footprint thus enhancing transparency. Unlike the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) which focuses on voluntary reporting, BRSR mandates quantitative key performance indicators including renewable energy and non-renewable energy consumption, greenhouse gas emissions, water usage, waste management and social metrics. This aims at balancing the need for economic growth and environmental accountability.

The FMCG sector is one of the most energy intensive industries and serves as a key contributor to Indian economy. With activities like manufacturing, processing, packaging, cold chain logistics and high brand visibility FMCG companies are exposed to greater scrutiny from consumers, investors and regulators (Munjal & Sharma, 2024). Dremptic (2020) found a positive correlation between firm size, company's ESG data and company's sustainability performance. Indian FMCG giants like Hindustan Uniliver Limited (HUL) and ITC Limited have set ambitious renewable energy targets (Businessworld, 2025) but it needs to be empirically seen whether or not the firm size has an influence on renewable energy adoption.

The study has two primary objectives. Firstly, to assess the BRSR framework role in the renewable energy adoption among Indian FMCG companies over three-year period FY22-FY25. Secondly, to determine whether market capitalization significantly influences the renewable energy adoption practice across firms. The study considers the empirical evidence related to SDG 7.2.1 and SDG 12.6.1 in emerging market context.

2. Literature Review

The literature review is organised around themes where first section examines the sustainability reporting and applies institutional theory to explain industrial pressures which drive renewable energy adoption. The second section reviews firm level determinants of renewable energy use with specific focus on FMCG sector. The third

section analyses the empirical evidence on the relationship between firm size and environmental investment and how the ambiguous findings necessitate the current research study.

2.1 Sustainability Reporting and Institutional Pressures

Early initiatives such as GRI provided guidelines to companies for disclosing ESG information on a voluntary basis. While voluntary reporting increased transparency it also suffered from selectivity, incomparability, and a lack of external assurance (Martínez et al, 2025). World agencies have since then moved towards mandatory reporting mechanisms like European Union's Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CRSD) and India's BRSR framework. Firms working in a corporate setting have to manage relationships at multiple levels such as with investors, customers, employees, regulators and government and the presence of transparency in reporting brings alignment between the firm's goals and the stakeholder expectations (Freeman, 1984). Legitimacy theory suggests that firms have to operate within the purview of societal norms and reporting serves as a medium which grants, maintains or repairs legitimacy (Suchman, 1995).

Studies like Ioannaou & Serafeim (2017), found that ESG disclosures improve Marquis et al (2016) showed, through the analysis of 4750 public companies in 45 countries during 2004-07, that firms are more likely to engage in selective disclosures in countries with less scrutiny and global norms. The term popularly used to refer selective disclosures by firms to show themselves in favourable light is 'greenwashing' without making operational changes. It becomes then more imperative to investigate whether mandatory reporting results in actual desired renewable transition or is just used by firms to showcase themselves as white knights.

Institutional theory (Dimaggio & Powell, 1983) identifies three pressures which can be used to explain the trends in global renewable energy adoption. Coercive pressures are a result of the regulatory environment in the form of BRSR disclosures being made mandatory for listed companies and punitive actions for noncompliance. Mimetic pressures are felt when the firms want to imitate their competitors or best

practices discovered possibly through benchmarking. Smaller firms which aspire to become like giants like HUL or ITC feel this pressure to mimic their actions as well which also results in legitimacy. Normative pressures result from the expectations of the stakeholders due to the prevalent norms in the scenario. With growing environmental concerns and consumer education it is general expectation to follow the sustainability norms. FMCG being more affected by high visibility faces this normative pressure more.

2.2 Determinants of Renewable Energy adoption in FMCG sector

Renewable energy adoption decision is influenced by external business pressures like regulatory policies and stakeholder activism as per Garrone et al (2010). Adoption by firms and its reporting may lead to benefits or sanctions accorded such as in the form of loyalty from consumers or leaving the business firm for a competitor. Studies carried out in past have highlighted that mandatory non-financial reporting was found to be associated with reductions in greenhouse gas emissions (Ioannou & Seraphim, 2019). It was also found that such greenhouse gas curtailing mostly doesn't document the renewable energy share in this change as they aggregate the carbon emissions or ESG scores and don't report the renewable energy in total consumption. The renewable energy share indicator SDG 7.2.1 documents this change more robustly by measuring the contribution of renewable energy consumption in carbon footprint reduction.

FMCG sector is an energy intensive industry with production, processing, packaging and cold chains involved and as they have more brand visibility, they face greater risk of loss of reputation by poor environmental performance (Munjal & Sharma, 2024). The influence of renewable energy adoption in FMCG sector has not been empirically tested in FY 23-FY25 and this study addresses this research gap.

2.3 Firm Size and Environmental Investment

The relationship between firm size and corporate environmental performance has been shown as positive by some research studies such as Drempetic et al (2020) and Brammer & Pavelin (2006). A meta-analysis carried out by Soysa et al (2022) studied 55 studies and found positive relationship between sustainability reporting

and firm size (correlation coefficient 0.376). A systematic literature review conducted by Farisyi et al (2022) showed that firm size is a highly studied factor of sustainability reporting domain but noted inconsistencies across individual studies. This shows that the relationship is not universally same as smaller firms might also be more agile benefitting from low barriers to entry such as in the form of roof top solar schemes.

Revell & Blackburn (2007) found that small and medium enterprises have faster adoption of renewable energy measures due to their simpler decision-making structures. D'Costa et al (2025) studied 200 NIFTY companies and found that ESG disclosures positively influence firm valuation but the moderating effect of firm size was negative. Ali and Singh (2024) analysed 9000 firms and found that firm size is positively associated with green practice adoption but the effect was moderated by other factors with different results. Female ownership positively affected green adoption in large firms but negatively in small and medium enterprises.

This study tries to test these contradicting theoretical perspectives and provides empirical evidence missing in FMCG sector in India.

3. Methodology

A longitudinal quantitative research design was used to examine the trends in renewable energy adoption over time and across firm sizes. A balanced panel approach was used assessing the NIFTY FMCG companies across three financial years, FY 23-FY25. ANOVA was used as the primary analytical technique as it is considered suitable for comparing means across multiple periods and is popularly used in longitudinal ESG and sustainability research.

3.1 Sampling & Data sources

Sampling frame consisted of all companies from the NIFTY FMCG Index where census sampling technique was used which means that all companies present in NIFTY FMCG Index were taken for which BRSR disclosure data was present for the aforementioned 3-year period. Census sampling technique eliminates errors arising due to sampling and is most suitable in case the population is small (Saunders et al,

2019). The NIFTY FMCG Index consists of 15 companies and as all companies had publicly available BRSR disclosure report for the 3-year study period, all companies were considered. So, the data consisted of 15 firms (N=15, total observations = 15 firms x 3 years = 45 observations) and while this sample size is modest it is representative of the population being complete and thus suitable for ANOVA.

The same set of companies was categorised into three groups i.e. small, medium and large based on their market capitalization.

Table 3.1: NIFTY FMCG companies-Market capitalization and energy consumption

Company Name	Market Capitalization	Non-Renewable (Giga Joule)		Renewable (Giga Joule)	
		2022-23	2023-2024	2022-23	2023-24
Britannia Industries Ltd.	142485	1324122	1775846	313633	503290
Colgate Palmolive (India) Ltd.	58784	213652	182752	11884	39894
Dabur India Ltd.	87797	349033	361722	354886	370987
Emami Ltd.	23551	124129	100234	4357	23148
Godrej Consumer Products Ltd.	118061	603727451	635397826	246851828	239056073
Hindustan Unilever Ltd.	531148	234806	155999	3484566	3570604
ITC Ltd.	501275	15380000	13185000	11505000	13198000
Marico Ltd.	94374	58984	57421	115384	118741
Nestle India Ltd.	238783	2603706	3129350	1328017	1680843
Patanjali Foods Ltd.	58400	7273015	7950233	1340145	1718216
Radico Khaitan Ltd	43168	17361968	47265356	36294418	71832924
Tata Consumer Products Ltd.	113728	153372	785562	174393	506120
United Breweries Ltd.	43579	365000	430000	1656000	1603000
United Spirits Ltd.	105254	48380	62919	815594	898613
Varun Beverages Ltd.	162318	1844443	1689484	845300	1150259

3.2 Data collection & Preparation

BRSR reports filed with Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI) by each company in the FMCG Index was the primary source of data which have the relevant indicators of renewable energy consumption. The reports were retrieved from National Stock Exchange (NSE) website as well as from the individual company portals. Under Principle 6 of BRSR framework quantitative disclosures are mandated with separate figures to be provided for renewable and non-renewable energy consumption measured in gigajoules (GJ).

Data extraction was performed independently by both authors to ensure accuracy and later cross-verification. Any discrepancies found were corrected through consensus building and wherever the data was available with different units were converted to standard units (Gigajoule and percentage) before analysis.

3.3 Hypotheses Formulation

Statistical analysis was carried out using IBM SPSS version 28 after formulating hypotheses statements describing the premise of the research,

The research objectives for this study necessitates the formulation of hypotheses as given below.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant change in the mean share of renewable energy to the total energy consumption of companies across time.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the ratio of renewable energy to the total energy consumption across different categories of companies based on market capitalization.

4 Findings & Interpretation

This section presents the empirical analysis of renewable energy adoption among the NIFTY FMCG Index companies over the three-year period. The analysis is organised into three parts with first part showing the descriptive statistics of renewable energy share (%) reported for each year, second part shows the ANOVA analysis for Hypothesis 1 and third part shows the analysis for Hypothesis 2.

4.1 Descriptive statistics

Table 4.1: Descriptive statistics- Mean Renewable Energy Consumption

	Mean (%)	Std. Deviation	N
Y1	45.80	30.093	15
Y2	47.67	26.543	15
Y3	55.20	28.097	15

The findings presented in the Table 4.1 reveals a progressive increase in the average renewable energy share across the three years. The mean value increased from 45.80% in Year 1 (Y1) to 47.67% in Year 2 (Y2), and further to 55.20% in Year 3 (Y3).

4.2 For Hypothesis 1

Table 4.2: Mauchly's Test of Sphericity^a

Measure: Year							
Within Subjects Effect	Mauchly's W	Approx. Chi-Square	df	Sig.	Epsilon ^b		
					Greenhouse-Geisser	Huynh-Feldt	Lower-bound
Factor1	.961	.516	2	.773	.963	1.000	.500
Tests the null hypothesis that the error covariance matrix of the orthonormalized transformed dependent variables is proportional to an identity matrix.							
a. Design: Intercept Within Subjects Design: factor1							
b. May be used to adjust the degrees of freedom for the averaged tests of significance. Corrected tests are displayed in the Tests of Within-Subjects Effects table.							

Table 4.3: Tests of Within-Subjects Effects

Measure: Year						
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared

factor1	Sphericity Assumed	742.978	2	371.489	15.009	.000	.517
	Greenhouse-Geisser	742.978	1.925	385.932	15.009	.000	.517
	Huynh-Feldt	742.978	2.000	371.489	15.009	.000	.517
	Lower-bound	742.978	1.000	742.978	15.009	.002	.517
Error(factor1)	Sphericity Assumed	693.022	28	24.751			
	Greenhouse-Geisser	693.022	26.952	25.713			
	Huynh-Feldt	693.022	28.000	24.751			
	Lower-bound	693.022	14.000	49.502			

Table 4.4: Pairwise comparisons

Measure: Year						
(I) factor1	(J) factor1	Mean Difference (I- J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	2	-1.867	1.971	1.000	-7.223	3.490
	3	-9.400*	1.661	.000	-13.915	-4.885
2	1	1.867	1.971	1.000	-3.490	7.223
	3	-7.533*	1.804	.003	-12.437	-2.629
3	1	9.400*	1.661	.000	4.885	13.915
	2	7.533*	1.804	.003	2.629	12.437
Based on estimated marginal means						
*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.						
b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.						

Hypothesis 1 stated that there is no significant change in the mean share of renewable energy to total energy consumption of companies across time. To test this hypothesis, a repeated measures ANOVA was conducted. The results of Mauchly's Test of Sphericity showed that the assumption of sphericity was not violated ($W = 0.961, p = 0.773$), indicating that the sphericity-assumed results could be interpreted. The ANOVA results revealed a statistically significant difference in the mean renewable energy share across the three years ($F = 15.009, p < 0.001$), with a partial eta squared value of 0.517, indicating a strong effect size. Further, pairwise comparisons using the Bonferroni adjustment showed that the mean difference between Year 1 and Year 3, as well as between Year 2 and Year 3, was statistically significant, whereas the difference between Year 1 and Year 2 was not significant. These findings indicate that renewable energy adoption significantly increased over time, particularly in Year 3. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, and it is concluded that there is a significant change in the mean share of renewable energy to total energy consumption of companies across the study period.

4.3 For Hypothesis 2

Table 4.5: Mauchly's Test of Sphericity^a

Measure: Firm Size							
Within Subjects Effect	Mauchly's W	Approx. Chi-Square	df	Sig.	Epsilon ^b		
					Greenhouse-Geisser	Huynh-Feldt	Lower-bound
Year	.949	.578	2	.749	.951	1.000	.500
Tests the null hypothesis that the error covariance matrix of the orthonormalized transformed dependent variables is proportional to an identity matrix.							
a. Design: Intercept + Market Cap Within Subjects Design: Year							
b. May be used to adjust the degrees of freedom for the averaged tests of significance. Corrected tests are displayed in the Tests of Within-Subjects Effects table.							

Table 4.6: Descriptive Statistics

	Market Cap	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Y1	Small	34.80	37.359	5
	Mid	58.40	23.923	5
	Large	44.20	29.132	5
	Total	45.80	30.093	15
Y2	Small	38.80	28.822	5
	Mid	55.40	25.706	5
	Large	48.80	28.279	5
	Total	47.67	26.543	15
Y3	Small	48.40	37.634	5
	Mid	64.40	20.107	5
	Large	52.80	27.779	5
	Total	55.20	28.097	15

Table 4.7: Tests of Within-Subjects Effects

Measure: Firm Size						
Source		Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Year	Sphericity Assumed	742.978	2	371.489	16.144	.000
	Greenhouse-Geisser	742.978	1.903	390.513	16.144	.000
	Huynh-Feldt	742.978	2.000	371.489	16.144	.000
	Lower-bound	742.978	1.000	742.978	16.144	.002
Year * MktCap	Sphericity Assumed	140.756	4	35.189	1.529	.225
	Greenhouse-Geisser	140.756	3.805	36.991	1.529	.228
	Huynh-Feldt	140.756	4.000	35.189	1.529	.225
	Lower-bound	140.756	2.000	70.378	1.529	.256
Error (Year)	Sphericity Assumed	552.267	24	23.011		
	Greenhouse-Geisser	552.267	22.831	24.190		
	Huynh-Feldt	552.267	24.000	23.011		
	Lower-bound	552.267	12.000	46.022		

Hypothesis 2 stated that there is no significant difference in the ratio of renewable energy to total energy consumption across different categories of companies based on market capitalization. A repeated measures ANOVA was conducted to examine the effect of market capitalization categories (small, mid, and large-cap companies) on renewable energy adoption over the three-year period. Mauchly's Test of Sphericity indicated that the assumption of sphericity was satisfied ($W = 0.949$, $p = 0.749$), allowing interpretation of the sphericity-assumed results. The descriptive statistics showed that mid-cap companies consistently reported higher mean renewable energy shares across all three years compared to small-cap and large-cap companies. However, the interaction effect, shown in Table 4.7, between Year and Market Capitalization was not statistically significant ($F = 1.529$, $p = 0.225$), indicating that the pattern of renewable energy adoption over time did not differ significantly among the three market capitalization categories. Although the main effect of Year was statistically significant ($F = 16.144$, $p < 0.001$), suggesting an overall increase in renewable energy adoption across all companies, the absence of a significant interaction effect implies that company size based on market capitalization did not significantly influence the ratio of renewable energy consumption. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted, indicating that there is no significant difference in renewable energy adoption.

5 Conclusion

The study examined the trend and variation in renewable energy adoption among NIFTY FMCG Index companies over the three-year duration (FY23-FY25) in the post BRSR period. The findings revealed a consistent increase in the mean share of renewable energy consumption, indicating that companies are gradually strengthening their focus on sustainability and clean energy practices. Additionally, the analysis based on market capitalization showed no significant difference in renewable energy adoption among different size of companies, thus denoting relatively similar contributions towards renewable energy adoption.

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